

SEARCH FOR NEW ANTIBACTERIAL COMPOUNDS. PART I

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Several 2-chloro-4-*tert.*-butylphenol esters of saturated fatty acids have been converted into the corresponding *o*-hydroxyketones by the Fries rearrangement. These have been reduced by the Clemmensen reduction to the corresponding 2-chloro-4-*tert.*-butyl-6-alkylphenols, which may be active antibacterials.

Baichwal, Jhaveri and Khorana (*J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1951, 10A, 498) observed that introduction of an alkyl or a halogen substituent in the phenol increased its activity. In a mono-substituted phenol the position of an alkyl group is not important. The bactericidal activity increases with the increase in the length of the alkyl chain up to a certain limit, beyond which activity falls. The maximum activity is reached at different levels for different micro-organisms. But when halogen and alkyl groups are both present in phenol, the consideration of the relative positions becomes important. Klarmann *et al.* (*J. Lab. Clin. Med.*, 1934, 19, 835 ; 1934, 20, 40) showed that *p*-alkyl derivatives of *o*-chlorophenol were efficient germicides. As regards the nature of the alkyl chain in the case of xylenols, the activity against *Staph. aureus* increases more rapidly with branched chain compounds, and in the cases of dihydroxy derivatives, branched chain compounds have been reported to possess unusually high activity (Baichwal *et al.*, *loc. cit.*). Keeping these facts in view, we have prepared various 2-chloro-4-*tert.*-butyl-6-alkylphenols which may possess much enhanced microbial potency.

Several saturated fatty acid esters of 2-chloro-4-*tert.*-butylphenol have been prepared by the action of appropriate acid chloride on the phenol, following the usual procedure (Tiwari and Tewari, this *Journal*, 1954, 31, 79). These esters were converted into the corresponding *o*-hydroxyketones by the Fries rearrangement, and the latter on the Clemmensen reduction furnished various 2-chloro-4-*tert.*-butyl-6-alkylphenols. The work on the evaluation of their bacteriostatic activity is in progress.

EXPERIMENTAL

Esters of 2-Chloro-4-tert.-butylphenol.—Eight new esters prepared are summarised in Table I.

TABLE I

Esters.	B.P.	Yield.	Mol. formula.	% Carbon.		% Hydrogen.	
				Found.	Calc.	Found.	Calc.
Acetate	180°/10 mm.	80%	C ₁₂ H ₁₅ O ₂ Cl	63.24	63.57	7.12	6.62
Propionate	129°/10	74	C ₁₃ H ₁₇ O ₂ Cl	64.45	64.85	7.24	7.07
Butyrate	162°/15	70	C ₁₄ H ₁₉ O ₂ Cl	65.22	66.01	7.15	7.47
Valerate	165°/21	74	C ₁₅ H ₂₁ O ₂ Cl	66.71	67.05	8.37	7.82
Caproate	157°/10	76	C ₁₆ H ₂₃ O ₂ Cl	68.47	67.97	8.06	8.14
Caprylate	187°/10	68	C ₁₈ H ₂₇ O ₂ Cl	69.17	69.56	8.91	8.70
Capriate	200°/12	70	C ₂₀ H ₃₁ O ₂ Cl	71.45	70.91	8.73	9.16
Laurate	212°/10	63	C ₂₂ H ₃₅ O ₂ Cl	72.22	72.02	9.67	9.55

TABLE II

o-Hydroxyketones and their 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazone derivatives.

2-Chloro-4-tert.-butylphenol-3-esters.	2-Hydroxy-3-chloro-5-tert.-butyl-esters.	B.P.	Yield.	Analysis of ketone.		M.P.	Mol. formula.	% Nitrogen.	
				% Carbon.	% Hydrogen.				Found.
Acetate	Acetophenone	142°/10	85%	63.41	6.62	224°	C ₁₈ H ₁₅ O ₅ N ₄ Cl	13.98	13.78
Propionate	Propiophenone	142°/10	80	64.42	7.52	227°	C ₁₉ H ₁₇ O ₅ N ₄ Cl	13.21	13.32
Butyrate	Butyrophenone	132°/10	80	66.50	7.67	176°	C ₂₀ H ₁₉ O ₅ N ₄ Cl	13.40	12.89
Valerate	Valerophenone	134°/20	75	67.44	7.91	185°	C ₂₁ H ₂₁ O ₅ N ₄ Cl	13.02	12.48
Caproate	Caprophenone	163°/13	71	68.21	8.56	163°	C ₂₂ H ₂₃ O ₅ N ₄ Cl	12.60	12.11
Caprylate	Caprylophenone	170°/10	72	69.82	8.52	127°	C ₂₄ H ₂₇ O ₅ N ₄ Cl	11.79	11.42
Capriate	Capriophenone	162°/13	68	71.32	9.54	185°	C ₂₅ H ₂₉ O ₅ N ₄ Cl	10.94	10.80
Laurate	Laurphenone	180°/22	68	72.40	9.12	163°	C ₂₆ H ₃₁ O ₅ N ₄ Cl	10.74	10.24

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Fries Rearrangement of the Esters.—A mixture of ester (1.0 M) and AlCl_3 (anhyd., 1.5 M) was gradually heated to 110° and the *o*-hydroxyketone was isolated as usual (Tiwari and Tewari, *loc. cit.*). The *o*-hydroxyketones, so obtained, conformed to the characteristic tests of these ketones (Coulthard, Marshall and Pyman, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 280). The *o*-hydroxyketones were further characterised by their 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazones which were recrystallised from glacial acetic acid (see Table II).

Clemmensen Reduction of 2-Chloro-4-tert.-butyl-6-acylphenols.—A mixture of zinc wool (20.0 g.), mercuric chloride (2.0 g.), HCl (conc., 5.0 c.c.) and water (20.0 c.c.) was stirred vigorously for 10 minutes. The supernatant liquid was then decanted off and the amalgamated zinc was liberally washed with water. It was covered by 30 c.c. of ethanol and 5.0 g. of *o*-hydroxyketone, and 10 c.c. of HCl (conc.) was added to it. The mixture was refluxed on a water-bath for 8 to 10 hours, during which 2 c.c. portions of HCl (conc.) were added after each hour.

After the period a drop of the liquid did not produce blue colour on a filter paper previously sprayed with aqueous ferric chloride. This indicated the absence of the *o*-hydroxyketone. Ethanol was then distilled off and the liquid was saturated with sodium chloride and extracted with ether. The ethereal extract was dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate and the ether removed by distillation. The product was then fractionally distilled. The various alkylphenols so obtained are summarised in Table III.

TABLE III

[R = 2-hydroxy-3-chloro-5-*tert.*-butyl-; P = 2-chloro-4-*tert.*-butylphenol]

<i>o</i> -Hydroxy- ketones	Chloroalkyl- phenol	B.P.	Yield.	Mol. formula.	% Carbon.		% Hydrogen.	
					Found.	Calc.	Found.	Calc.
R-acetophenone	6-Ethyl-P	$139^\circ/29\text{mm.}$	64%	$\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{17}\text{OCl}$	67.91	67.78	8.41	8.00
R-propiophenone	6- <i>n</i> -Propyl-P	$119^\circ/21$	62	$\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{19}\text{OCl}$	68.42	68.87	8.60	8.39
R-butyrophenone	6- <i>n</i> -Butyl-P	$146^\circ/11$	58	$\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{21}\text{OCl}$	69.71	69.85	8.83	8.73
R-valerophenone	6- <i>n</i> -Pentyl-P	$163^\circ/42$	62	$\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{23}\text{OCl}$	71.13	70.73	9.45	9.04
R-caprophenone	6- <i>n</i> -Hexyl-P	$150^\circ/12$	58	$\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{25}\text{OCl}$	71.00	71.51	9.78	9.31
R-caprylophenone	6- <i>n</i> -Octyl-P	$153^\circ/11$	52	$\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{29}\text{OCl}$	72.64	72.86	10.20	9.78
R-capriophenone	6- <i>n</i> -Decyl-P	$150^\circ/11$	52	$\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{33}\text{OCl}$	73.78	73.95	10.60	10.17
R-lauraphenone	6- <i>n</i> -Dodecyl-P	$170^\circ/11$	50	$\text{C}_{22}\text{H}_{37}\text{OCl}$	75.41	74.91	10.11	10.50

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